

PRACTICE OF WORKING WITH BOOK DEPARTMENT AND ITS USEFUL ASPECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556293>

Annotation: The purpose of writing this article is to show the importance of books in human life, how much is the world view, unique thinking, how to focus, increase reading imagination, in addition to learning foreign languages, the treatment of family members to their parents and love to their loved ones. just to show that it is appropriate:

Key words: book, thought, stress, world view, unique idea, brain activity, vocabulary, respect, family member, 24 hours, 1095 hours, 365 days.

Reading helps to generate new and unique ideas. Reading encourages us to think. Sometimes, our dreams are related to the book we read and enjoyed. Also, reading enriches our worldview. A person gets new thoughts and bright ideas through reading. Unknowingly, a person is inspired to read, which gives rise to new and different thoughts. Reading concentrates the human mind and increases focus. In the process of reading, all attention is paid to the read story and work. A person pays more attention to books than to other things. The human brain cannot handle different activities at the same time. Therefore, it is much easier for a person who has read a lot to concentrate. Reading increases imagination. When we read about places that are unfamiliar to us, our perception and imagination begin to create images in our brain, and thus the images are stored in our memory. Therefore, the imagination and creativity of our perception is strengthened by reading books. Reading makes learning a foreign language easier. Regular reading helps to easily understand and remember new words when learning other languages. Scientists have proven that a person learning a foreign language can master that language in a short time by regularly reading the literature of that language. Reading together improves the relationship between parents and children. When a person teaches his child to read books, he must first of all be an example in this work. Psychologists believe that in the process of reading books together, a special relationship is established between parents and children. They say that such an attitude does not appear when watching TV together. Reading makes you smarter. Books are a real treasure trove of resources and new knowledge. Also, they are much cheaper than the education of various training courses at the

moment. The more books one reads, the more one's intelligence and ability to think deeply increases. At the same time, the more a person reads books on various topics, the better he will improve his knowledge and master the art of communication. Reading strengthens the brain. A person usually has a lot of time to think about the book he has read. Emory University scientists proved that the mental capacity of a person who reads a book is in a high state for several days. The authors of the study emphasize that reading books strengthens the nerve fibers in the brain.

Reading improves our language skills. Reading literature in a foreign language requires a lot of effort at first, but it helps to increase our vocabulary. When understanding another language, sometimes it is necessary to translate its various parts and look them up in a dictionary. Reading not only increases vocabulary, but also general literacy. Regardless of which language you study, you will be able to learn how the context of a sentence is created through reading. Reading reduces stress. When a person is reading a book, at that moment he is not thinking about any tasks or worries. When reading a book, we often settle down in a way that is convenient for us. Our body does not perform any special action at all and rests. Breathing slows down and we relax. We begin to imagine ourselves that the image of events happening in the world is reflected in the book through words. The reason for all this is that reading reduces stress. Reading serves to increase our vocabulary. According to research, it has been proven that people who read books have a higher vocabulary compared to other people, and because of this, they express the expressions they want to say to others very easily. In short, the more you read, the more vocabulary you will acquire. Also, books are a treasure trove of knowledge.

You know that this world is only for five days, we came to this life only to leave a little bit of knowledge and a good name, it is not an exaggeration if we spend this little bit of time to learn and acquire knowledge in order to spend our life meaningfully. Imagine if we spend at least three hours of our 24 hours a day on this work, i.e. reading a book, that means 1095 hours in a year, we can read a lot of books in this period of time. Let's imagine that if you leave your daily life to this virtual world, even then these twenty-four hours will not pass, but never forget that you will be brought up not to be a manager, but to be managed, and the choice of the path is up to you. . My final message to all the people reading this article is to never stop learning.

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